

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY, TSKALTUBO (GEORGIA) WATER RADON HORMESIS AND ORAL MICROBIOLOGY

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Abstract

Combined effect of “Rada Dent” and Tskhaltubo water (inhalation of Tskhaltubo water and using it as a mouthwash) slowly reduces and cures inflammation caused by periodontitis and gingivitis, which can be explained by the unique characteristics of “Rada Dent” and Tskaltubo water. At the present moment, information on the characteristics of only a few thousand microorganisms making up normal microflora of the oral cavity is available. These are bacteria, viruses, fungi and protozoa.

The majority of Gram-positive Cocci in the oral cavity is represented by heterogeneous group of Streptococci, which are active participants in damaging hard tooth and periodontal tissues.

“Rada Dent” and Tskaltubo water hormesis proved successful in slowing down and curing oral inflammation.

Keywords: Photodynamic therapy, radonized water, periodontitis, gingivitis, microflora.

Introductoin

Tskaltubo mineral water , located in Georgia (<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CAMQw7AJahcKEwjww9LXzdj4AhUAAAAAHQAAA AAAg&url=https%3A%2F%2Ftskaltuboresort.ge%2Feng&psig=AOv-Vaw2bzLOv3T5lV5ch4lQA4pvn&ust=1656796325261966>) is distinguished by the fact that each ingredient is below the lower threshold of the norm.

Chemical composition of Tskaltubo springs is stable and unchanged in time. Juxtaposition of chemical analyses conducted throughout the recent 70-80 year corroborates the mentioned.

Tskaltubo mineral water is distinguished by solid physical and chemical characteristics. It contains noble gas – Radon, large amount of Nitrogen and Helium. It belongs to the category of waters containing small amount of Radon (1-2,7 nCi/L; or 3-7,5 unit ; or 40-100 Bq), Chlorine-Hydrocarbonate-Sulfate, Sodium-Magnesium-Calcium – total mineralization 0,7-0,8 g/L. 24-hour yield for the springs amounts to 13-15 million liters. Highly effective medicinal and preventive effect of the spring waters is due to complex composition and peculiar combination of principle components composed of sodium. The natural temperature (+33-35°C) allows to use it without warming up.

Biologically active microelements (Iodine, Bromine, Manganese, Lithium, Bohrium, Zinc, Strontium, and Copper) have been discovered in the Tskaltubo mineral waters, which play an important role in the vitality of the body.

20-25% of the world’s adult population suffer from periodontal diseases, most widespread of which are periodontitis and gingivitis.

At the moment, information on the characteristics of only a few thousand microorganisms that make up normal microflora of the oral cavity is available . Among them are bacteria, viruses, fungi and protozoa. Amid the microbes of the oral cavity, autochthonous and allochthones variety are more prominent. Allochthones-immigrants are microflora from other biotopes (nose and throat, intestines and etc.) of the host and environment. From autochthonous microflora, obligate, which always live in the oral cavity and temporary-transitory, which is frequently made up of pathogenic or conditionally pathogenic bacteria.

The majority of gram-positive oral Cocci are heterogeneous group of Streptococci of low virulence, which are active participants of processes that lead to damaging periodontal tissue [1]. These are Streptococcus mutans, S.mitis, S. Salivarius. The second group of gram-positive Cocci are Peptococci. Peptococci are most frequently associated with Fusobacteria and spirochetes during caries, pulpitis, periodontitis, and dental abscess.

Gram-negative anaerobic Cocci in the oral cavity are Veillonella and gram-positive bacillus are Lactobacillus; Gram-negative anaerobic and microaerophilic bacteria most frequently belong to Bacteroides group; and yeasts named Candida produce vitamins essential for Lactobacteria to grow. The latter produce lactic acid during metabolism that causes increasing acidity of the environment, hinders adhesion and yeast colonization, which in turn leads to reduction in the number of vitamins essential to restrict growth in some microorganisms.

The oxygen level is significantly lowered in the periodontal and pseudo-pockets, mucous folds. This creates advantageous conditions for development of

such anaerobes as Fusobacteria, Bacteriodes, Leptotrichia, Spirochaete [2]. 100 million anaerobic microorganism could be in 1 ml of saliva [3]. The nature of food has a big influence on the qualitative and quantitative index of oral microflora: increased amount of sucrose leads to increased share of Streptococci and Lactobacteria, however glucose does not have such influence. While these processes are ongoing, toxic genes gain control over ADP-ribosyltransferase enzyme activity, which produces a cascade of reactions and breaks down cyclic adenosine monophosphate acid (AMP) synthesis, therefore, breaking down cyclic synthesis in the given cell.[4]

The toxicity of endotoxins is noticed during high concentration levels. They can activate complimentary systems, for example, blood coagulation, they impact enzyme systems of the body, etc. Platelet membrane, macrophages, lymphocytes and capillary endothelium have binding receptors. Endotoxin activity is based upon their concentration. In low doses, they can activate phagocytosis and other protective reactions [5.6]. Pathogenic enzymes synthesize reactions, which are directed at producing toxic products or disrupt cell and tissue. Fibrinolysis and hyaluronidase facilitate toxin spread, due to which microbes easily penetrate the tissue and cause its disruption, and phospholipase causes necrosis. As for Staphylococci and Streptococci, hemolysins lyse erythrocytes and leucocytes [7.8].

Plasma coagulase of Staphylococci and other microorganisms – peptidase activates blood coagulation through catalyzing prothrombin into thrombin and creates fibrin layer around microbial cells. We studied microbial characteristics in the oral fluid during periodontitis [9]. Strains of microflora were identified in each

patient before starting a treatment. The most frequently studied strains by us are as follows: Streptococcus intermedius, Prevotella spp., Fusobacterium spp.

Principal objective for us is to study a method for photodynamic therapy, its effect on inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity. Photodynamic therapy has been broadly used during the last decade [2]. This method of treatment was popular both in treating oncological and non-oncological, inflammatory diseases (such as gingivitis and periodontitis) in the fields of stomatology and medicine.

Material and methods.

We observed compound effect of photosensitizer “Rada Dent”, machine “Photodin-K” and inhalation of Radon in Tskhaltubo water and using it as a mouthwash. At the beginning, once every 6 months and later after 1 or 2 years. Combination therapy includes scaling and root instrumentation, photodynamic therapy [10] and Radon inhalation. The combination therapy allows us to treat mild forms of gingivitis and periodontitis in patients without antibiotics or other medications.

The main reasons the patients present to us are bleeding gums, unpleasant smell, and insufficient hygiene. The insufficient hygiene is the principal reason for forming a bacterial biofilm.

The patients were healthy and systemic diseases were not recorded, which has a huge impact on the oral mucosa.

Stabilized, resistant microflora is mainly represented with microaerophilic Streptococci in the oral fluid: Streptococcus sanguis, Streptococcus salivarius, Streptococcus mitis, also Enterobacter spp. and Lactobacillus spp.

Table 1

Microflora	Before treatment		After treatment	
	N	%	N	%
<i>St. intermedius</i>	9	60	8	46,4
<i>St. haemolyticus</i>	1	6,8	0	0
<i>Str. Sanguis</i>	10	72,9	0	0
<i>Str. Mitis</i>	10	72,0	7	42
<i>Str. Faecium</i>	0	0	0	0
<i>Str. Salivarius</i>	13	81	11	67,2
<i>Str. Viridians</i>	6	34,1	5	27,6
<i>C. albicans</i>	0	0	4	27,2
<i>Lactobacillus spp.</i>	2	13,3	2	13,3
<i>Prevotella spp.</i>	12	81	5	25,5
<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>	1	6,6	1	6,6
<i>Fusobacterium spp.</i>	4	27,1	2	14,1

n – Number of patients (n=15) in the group

Microbial characteristics: after treating mild and average forms of periodontitis with photodynamic therapy and Tskaltubo water hormesis, frequency of potential periodontopathic pathogen (Prevotella spp., Bacteriodes spp., Streptococcus intermedius) production was observed to reduce alongside with stabilized resistant oral microflora (Streptococcus sanguis, Streptococcus salivarius, Streptococcus salivarius, St.) and increase in the frequency of candida albicans production was recorded (Table 1).

Quantitative assessment of microorganisms and change in the numbers gives us a more objective data. For statistical convenience, CFU/ml was recalculated with a common logarithm. After treatment, significant reduction of microorganisms was observed compared to the data obtained before treatment ($p < 0.05$) and some variety totally disappeared.

(Table 2)

Microbial characteristics: treating patients with mild and average forms of periodontitis with photodynamic therapy [11] and Tskaltubo water hormesis (lgCFU/ml, $M \pm \delta$)

Table 2

Microorganisms	Before treatment	After treatment
<i>St. aureus</i>	5,7	3
<i>Str. Intermedius</i>	7,4±0,4	2,3±0,4
<i>Str. Haemolyticus</i>	4,7	–
<i>Str. Sangvis</i>	5,6±0,3	–
<i>Str. Mitis</i>	7,7±0,1	1,9±0,3
<i>Str. Salivarius</i>	6,8±0,4	2,4±0,3
<i>C. albicans</i>	–	3,6±0,1

After the treatment, the majority of Streptococci characteristic to normal flora - *Streptococcus sanguis*, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus mitis* – reduced significantly from lg 7.7 ± 0.1 to lg 1.9 ± 0.3, and the representatives of *Streptococcus* almost totally disappeared. The number of *Streptococcus intermedius*, *Stafilococcus aureus* significantly reduced and *Streptococcus haemolyticus* totally disappeared. However, the number of *Candida* increased to lg 3.6 ± 0.1.

Results and discussion:

To illustrate clinical course of gingivitis, we are providing an excerpt from a patient's outpatient card, who was under our observation. A patient D. M. presented in the Department of Stomatology complaining of unpleasant smell, bleeding gum during brushing the teeth, sometimes during biting solid food, gum swelling and hyperemia.

According to the patient, gum bleeding started approximately 3 months ago. They did not visit a doctor, did not undergo any kind of treatment.

During oral examination, oral mucosa is pale pink, shiny, damp. Gingival margin on the upper and lower jaw is hyperemic, interdental papilla are swollen, bleeding was observed during probing, false pockets, difficulty of brushing the teeth due to bleeding and gum swelling, a lot of soft dental plaque. Front teeth of lower jaw is covered with tartar. IG (Green-Vermillion) = 2.1. Clinical attachment is not lost. Loose teeth are not observed. PMA index = 19%; PI = 1.8.

Orthopantomogram: Bone tissue unchanged.

Diagnosis: Gingivitis caused by bacterial biofilm.

Microbiological study of insides of gingival sulcus identified: *Streptococcus intermedius* 5 × 10⁶ CFU/ml, *Streptococcus mitis* 10³ CFU/ml.

A fluorescent diagnostic device was used for diagnostics. It allows us to identify healthy, inflamed and atypical cells. The difference is color-coded.

Scaling and under gum treatment of pseudo-pockets, photodynamic therapy – 5 visits, every other day [12, 13].

Recommendation – complete oral hygiene, patient's motivation, 1 week course of inhalations with radonized Tskhaltubo water and using it as a mouthwash. Alpha rays of Radon in Tskhaltubo water plays a significant role in regulating inflammation and microflora and ultimately in maintaining homeostasis.

On the fifth day of the treatment, periodontal tissues were ameliorated. Unpleasant smell disappeared, gum bleeding was almost gone. After the course of the therapy, we observed relief in inflammation. After undergoing treatment and recommendation course, microbiological study observed the following: *Candida albicans* 3 × 10³ CFU/ml. PMA = 6%; PI = 0.3; SBI = 0.

Examinations to check the state were held according to the indicated period. After 3 months, the patient no longer had complaints, clinical signs of inflammation were not observed and did not need treatment. The patient continued maintenance therapy, examinations held after 6 and 12 months did not display deterioration, which was corroborated by clinical indices. 6 months later: OHI-S = 1.1; PMA = 9%; PI = 1.3; SBI = 1,1; 12 months later - OHI-S = 1.1; PMA = 9%; PI = 1.3; SBI = 1.1.

Pic.1

Standard clinical index dynamics in patient D. M. was positive after using antibacterial therapy for treating mild form of periodontitis. Thus, the obtained data points at long-term clinical effects of photodynamic therapy, Tskaltubo water Radon hormesis and microbiological study of the oral cavity.

The patient sticks with the rules of oral hygiene and occasionally uses recommended dose of inhalation of Tskaltubo radonized water.

Conclusion

Photosensitizer “Rada Dent”, device “Photodin-K” and inhalation of Radon in Tskaltubo water has combined effect. Through a non-invasive method used once in 6 months at the beginning and 1 or 2 years later, we managed to treat and prevent oral mucosa and periodontal disease without antibiotics. On the grounds of the treatment statistical data we can state that treatment of mild forms of periodontitis with the above mentioned combined method gives us a positive dynamics, which is reinforced with amelioration of clinical signs.

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